

Socio-Economic and Demographic Determinants of Fertility in Azerbaijan: the Role of Son Preference

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Abstract

The paper analyses fertility and reproductive behaviour in Azerbaijan with a focus on the impact of socio-economic and cultural factors. Particular attention is paid to the impact of mothers' level of education, economic wealth well-being of families and cultural preference for sons. The study is based on the data from the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) 2000, 2006 Azerbaijan Demographic and Health Survey (AzDHS 2006), and the Republic of Azerbaijan's Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population (MLSP) survey for 2015–2017. Econometric methods allowed to identify the relationship between having many children in a family and such factors as mother's higher education, level of family wealth and son preference.

Keywords

demographic transition in Azerbaijan, fertility, reproductive behaviour

JEL codes: J13, J18

Introduction

Over the past 50 years, Azerbaijan's population has tripled due to natural and migratory growth¹, exceeding 10 million in 2020. The positive migration balance sustained over a long period of time, as well as the United Nations projections that the country's population would reach 11 million by the mid-2030s (United Nations 2019), may create the illusion that an active demographic policy is not needed, but the situation is not so clear-cut.

¹ Source: The State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan (URL: <https://www.stat.gov.az/>; accessed on 20 April 2022).

Figure 1. Evolution of total fertility rate (TFR) for all births for 1980–2021 in Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Turkey. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on World Population Prospects 2022 data (URL: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/igo/>; accessed on 08 November 2023)

Although in Azerbaijan the fertility rate started to decline at higher levels than in the neighbouring Caucasus countries (Fig. 1), by 2021 the total fertility rate fell to 1.66 children per woman, which is below the population replacement level. In Armenia, the total fertility rate was slightly lower (1.57 in 2021), in Georgia and Turkey, higher but not by much, while in Kazakhstan it has been increasing over the past two decades. Fluctuations and even the growth of the total fertility rate in the post-Soviet states could be associated with changes in their ethnic composition, with increased proportion of the population of the titular nation (ethnic group), which could cause a short-term increase in the indicator, although in Kazakhstan it lasted longer. This makes it difficult to compare the evolution of the indicators. In Azerbaijan during the COVID-19 pandemic, the fertility decline continued along with an increase in the average age of the mother at the birth of her first child (Fig. 2).

(Bongaarts and Hodgson 2022) points to women’s better access to education and, consequently, women’s expanded labour market participation and better access to contraception as the main factors in fertility decline in developing countries. The long-term fertility decline in Azerbaijan can also be explained by the women’s higher level of education and an enabling environment for their employment, which may delay having children. In the short term, changes in fertility levels may result from postponing or avoiding births of higher-order children in times of economic crises due to higher unemployment and decline in household wealth.

One of the factors that may contribute to a higher fertility rate is a preference for sons due to the tradition, namely the preference for male offsprings as the bearers of the family name,

Figure 2. Evolution of the average age of women at first birth and evolution of the total fertility rate (TFR) for all births for 1980-2022 in Azerbaijan. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on the Republic of Azerbaijan's State Statistical Committee data (URL: <https://www.stat.gov.az/>; accessed on 20 April 2022)

which, combined with limited access to contraception, could cause either a higher birth rate or a high rate of induced abortion.

Earlier research (Kazenin and Kozlov 2020) focused on socio-economic factors that may affect if families have many children² in Central Asia, and women's higher level of education was linked to the reduction of births in households.

However, in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the surveys were conducted without using the tools necessary to determine the causal relationship between the indicators (Shukyurov 2020). The microdata that may have been used in the surveys do not adequately reflect the current situation, as the last publicly available global AzDHS (Azerbaijan Demographic and Health Survey) was conducted in 2006 (DHS, 2006). The AzDHS 2011 survey database is still not available. Therefore, the 2015-2017 survey data provided by the Republic of Azerbaijan's Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population remain the most relevant.

Identifying the factors that affect fertility is important from the perspective of choosing the direction of the demographic and family policy. If the preference for sons affects fertility, then encouraging the birth of daughters is a necessary measure for long-term demographic and social stability. And if the fertility rate depends currently more on households' financial capacity, then financial assistance measures for households based on the number and age of children will have a short-term effect.

The novelty of this study is a comparison of the results of all currently available databases on the Republic of Azerbaijan and an empirical study of two main indicators, namely the transition to higher birth orders and the mother's average age at first birth, based on individual data.

The study aims to identify socio-economic and demographic factors associated with fertility decline based on the microdata from the following surveys conducted in Azerbaijan

² A large family or a family with many children is defined here as a family with a minimum of three children.

in 2000–2017: MICS 2000 (MICS, 2006); DHS 2006 (DHS, 2006); and a 2015–2017 survey conducted by the Republic of Azerbaijan’s Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population (MLSP).

Review of research findings on the relationship between socio-economic factors and fertility rates

The impact of modernisation on demographic processes is a debatable topic (Kazenin 2020; Pörtner 2022; Maitra 2004). It is customary to divide the factors affecting fertility into demographic factors (age, marital status) and socio-economic factors (father’s and mother’s level of education, household income, household location (urban or rural), use of contraception, etc.).

In this paper, modernisation processes that affect fertility refer to accelerated urbanisation, the weakening of tradition (which manifests itself in women’s increased independence and mobility, better opportunities for gender equality and reduced son preference), and increased women’s participation in the labour force.

In the literature, there are several areas of research into the relationship between the modernisation factors and the national fertility rate: in Central Asia (Kazenin 2020) and India (Pörtner 2022), preference for sons and selective abortion play a role, while in Africa the issue of contraception is a factor (Kelodjoue 2015). Studies based on data collected in the Philippines, Malaysia (Trussell et al. 1985), Mexico (LaVine et al. 1987) and some African countries (Maitra 2004) examined the impact of women’s level of education on fertility. Socio-economic and demographic factors affecting fertility are:

Son preference

Son preference may have competing impacts on fertility depending on access to abortion. The issue of causes and consequences of the skewed ratio of boys to girls at birth was raised repeatedly in research (Basu and De Jong, 2010; Guilmoto 2013), including those relating to the Caucasus (Guilmoto 2013; Michael et al. 2013; Duthé et al. 2012).

In the paper on gender relations, social inequality and fertility in Central Asia (Kazenin and Kozlov 2020), the authors put forward several hypotheses that, “other things being equal”, one can expect “son preference” to be more effective as a tool to increase the fertility rate. The researchers’ main question was: “Does the absence of sons increase the probability of a woman having a third or fourth child?” The study confirmed the hypothesis that families with only two daughters are more likely to have a third and fourth child: it follows that the son preference encourages higher fertility in the absence of widespread access to selective abortion.

Advances in perinatal sex diagnosis technology, along with an increased access to selective abortion, have led to an increase in abortion in countries with strong traditions, such as India. Apart from tradition, son preference may be due to policies aimed at reducing the fertility rate, combined with the economic need for sons to provide for parents in their old age. The One Family, One Child policy in China is an obvious example (Li et al. 2011).

Based on the above studies, there is a potential association of son preference with shorter birth spacing (Jayachandran and Kuziemko 2011) and worse health indicators for daughters in families without sons (Whitworth and Stephenson 2002).

In Azerbaijan, son preference impacts fertility through a socio-cultural tradition that considers sons to be the bearers of the family name and the ones to support parents in their old age. This causes families without sons to continue to strive to have a male offspring, which in turn can increase the total number of children in the family. This behaviour persists even in the context of urbanisation and modernisation of society, highlighting deeply embedded cultural norms and their influence on reproductive strategies. The traditional preference for sons influences families' decisions to continue having children until a son is born, which may increase the total number of children in the family. At the same time, access to perinatal sex diagnosis and selective abortion allow families to control the sex of the baby in the early stages of pregnancy. These two practices have different socio-economic consequences and cause different demographic developments.

Women's education and employment

Women's education is an important modernisation factor. The correlation between a high level of mother's education and lower fertility rate is discussed in many studies. Some studies in Africa (Maitra 2004) and Mexico (LeVine et al. 1991) showed that the relationship is not strictly linear. It is not a matter of higher or lower level of education, but of reaching a particular level of education. This level is typically equivalent to the completion of secondary education.

Becker argued that children are a costly good and that the decision-making about having a child is based on a cost-benefit comparison (Becker 1960). So, on the one hand, people with higher education, therefore, a higher chance of finding a high-paying job, have a greater propensity to have children because their higher income makes it easier to cover the high costs of child upbringing. However, in a later paper, the same author suggests that the motive of high-income individuals may not be to have another child, but to improve the quality of parenting of the children they already have (Becker and Lewis 1973).

This is also corroborated in more recent studies. Day states that an increase in women's net wages tend to lead to a negative substitution effect on the demand for children, which can be stronger than the positive income effect. This often causes an initial decline in fertility as parents prioritise the quality of children over their quantity (Day 2018). The reverse effect has also been proven, so that during economic shocks that cause a decrease in women's wages, the latter's impact on fertility through income and substitution effects can be traced. The income effect in this case usually involves an intention to have fewer children, while the substitution effect related to the time spent on parenting can lead to having more children during economic downturn (Ferreira and Schady 2009).

Hotz notes that the relative strength of the income effect and substitution effect determines the impact of higher wages on the fertility rate (Hotz et al. 1997). Nowadays, a child is a luxury rather than a capital investment. The substitution effect means that as wages rise, time becomes more expensive, causing people to work more while spending less time on other activities, including child-rearing. Whereas the income effect, conversely, means that people with sufficiently high wages and therefore more money to spend are more likely to plan for a larger family and less likely to think about work. A shorter birth spacing allows parents to use the economies of scale in child-rearing. For example, it takes less time to care for two children in the family than twice the time needed to care for one child (Hotz et al. 1997).

A study on Azerbaijan data

There are only a limited number of studies on fertility decline in Azerbaijan, with the authors mostly referring to the same source, the 2006 DHS study, or limiting themselves to descriptive statistics of macro-indicators.

A. Shukyurov's paper on "Demographic transition in Azerbaijan" considers several key indicators that can be used to assess the completion of the demographic transition in fertility in the country: the total fertility rate (TFR), age-specific fertility coefficients, and the mother's age at the birth of her first and last child (Shukyurov 2020). This approach does not provide insight into the socio-economic factors of fertility trends.

The 2015 UNFPA study of the demographic transition in Azerbaijan assessed both the total fertility level and its evolution and birth spacing and secondary sex ratio. The authors note that birth spacing increases with each subsequent birth to the extent that it takes twice as long before the birth of a third child as before the birth of the first two children. The secondary sex ratio may differ between rural and urban areas: the urban indicator ranged from 230 to 62 boys per 100 girls, while in rural areas, from 394 to 72 boys per 100 girls (Avdeev 2015). This proves a significant difference between urban and rural areas, which should be considered in research.

Another study on the reasons for selective abortion in Azerbaijan was conducted by UNFPA in 2014 (Yüksel-Kaptanoğlu et al. 2014). Among the motives, son preference was highlighted. The qualitative and quantitative research showed that respondents prefer to have more sons for several reasons, the most common of which are continuation of lineage and family name, support in old age, as well as defence of the country, which was inspired by the atmosphere of the time. Respondents of the qualitative research, when asked about son preference, believed it was more of a rural phenomenon, while recognising the scarcity of women in the country.

N. Verdieva in (Verdieva 2019) argues that the decline in the total fertility rate is mostly due to the reduction of higher-order births.

Demographic waves influence the ratio of proportions of different-order births. Also, an increase in the proportion of first children at some point in time will lead to an increase in the proportion of second, third, etc. children after a certain time. This amount of time may depend on both socio-economic shocks and demographic policy measures. The proportion of second children is currently growing in Azerbaijan. The proportion of first children is beginning to decline due to a decrease in the number of potential young mothers. There are more cases of five or more births in rural areas compared to urban areas. But in general, the birth-order dynamics is identical between urban and rural areas.

The conclusions from the analysis of factors conducive to fertility and having many children are given in the cause-effect diagram (Fig. 3).

Having higher education can affect the number of children in the family both directly and indirectly. A mother's university degree may delay the birth of a first child and thus reduce the probability of eventually having many children. Also, higher education increases mother's chances of getting a job and thus may lead to postponing the first birth until later. According to the literature review, a higher family income may shift the preference from having more children to providing better parenting for fewer children. Urban residence is also associated with higher income and higher educational attainment, which means that urbanisation can have a negative impact on the number of children in a family.

Age group is a control variable in many intergenerational studies. Older cohorts may be much more strongly affected by tradition than younger cohorts. Tradition, in turn, influ-

Figure 3. Cause-effect diagram of factors conducive to having many children. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on literature review

ences the preference for sons as the bearers of the family name, which can influence if the family gets large in several ways. Firstly, through a positive influence because the parents will keep trying until a boy is born. Secondly, through selective abortion, which results in longer birth intervals thereby shortening the reproductive life. The use of contraception can reduce the total number of abortions, allowing women more time during their reproductive years and improving their reproductive health, as well as reducing the fertility rate.

Microdata-based assessment of the relationship between socio-economic and demographic factors and fertility rates in the Republic of Azerbaijan

As follows from the literature review, modernisation factors are significant in fertility decline. The factors can be divided into several groups:

- Economic: urban residence, higher education, employment, and household earnings;
- Social: son preference, use of contraception;
- Demographic: age group.

Based on the literature review, the following hypotheses were proposed:

H1: Higher education, higher material wealth and urban residence have a negative effect on whether the family is going to get large.

The first hypothesis was tested using the data from MICS 2000, DHS 2006, and the MLSP (Azerbaijan's Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population) survey for 2015-2017 on individual socio-economic characteristics of female respondents in reproductive age. An ordered logit model was used to identify the direction of the association of the indicators with higher-order births.

H2: Son preference is positively associated with having many children.

As shown in the factor diagram in the previous chapter (Fig. 3), son preference can be related to fertility in two ways: by increasing the chances of having many children or by reducing the number of births through selective abortion. Based on past research, it is hypothesised that the positive factor outweighs the negative one so that son preference has a positive effect on fertility.

Characterisation of surveys

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics of all quantitative variables selected for hypothesis testing. Descriptive statistics for all the three databases were aggregated into one table to allow tracing the dynamics of the main quantitative indicators.

Before reviewing the variables, the specifics of each sample should be explained. The 2000 and 2006 surveys took place throughout the Republic of Azerbaijan, while the 2015–2017 survey took place in three economic districts, Shaki-Zagatala, Aran, and Lankaran. The sample sizes were also different: 7,021 respondents were interviewed for MICS 2000; 8,444 respondents, for 2006 DHS; and 1,621 respondents, for the MLSP survey. All respondents were women of reproductive age from 15 to 49 years old (18 to 54 years in the 2015–2017 survey).

The 2015–2017 sample is older than the MICS and DHS samples, as shown by the median age of respondents, as the sample included the 50–54 age group. The indicator of secondary education in years increased in 2006 compared to 2000, which, with an equal median of 10 years, means that more respondents continued their education beyond the bachelor's degree and more respondents completed their secondary education. The age at first birth did not change dramatically over the six years between the first two surveys, however, the third survey showed an increase in this indicator, which may indicate the impact of modernisation on fertility. The wealth index represents the distribution of respondents into five quantiles of household wealth.

The number of children in the family also varies across surveys (Table 1). In the 2015–2017 survey, there were almost no respondents without children. The diagram in Figure 4 shows the prevalence of respondents having two or more children, which gives 2.45 of children per woman in this sample. Whereas in the first two surveys, the distribution of the number of children is almost identical.

The first hypothesis relates to the transition from one fertility level to another. This requires estimating the proportion of each group as a function of the number of children in the total number of observations; this frequency distribution is shown in Fig. 4. The diagram shows two large groups: respondents with two and respondents with three children. Also important for the analysis is the group of respondents with four children. By analysing these particular groups, it is possible to identify a decrease in the proportion of higher-order births. First births will not be included in the analysis, as they are not an issue at the moment.

The study also used binary variables, the distribution of which is presented in Table 2.

The survey conducted by Azerbaijan's Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population (MLSP) concerns the rural population to a greater extent than the urban population. The 2000 and 2006 survey data are closer to reality, with the proportions of the urban population in these years being 51.1% and 52.6%, respectively.³

The change in the proportion of respondents with higher education was caused by a feature of the questionnaires. In 2006, there was no distribution by type of educational institution and respondents were divided into three groups with the third group including people with higher education. Other variables are given in the table to show that for each group of binary variables there is a sufficient number of respondents so that the final model estimate is not biased.

3 Source: The State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan (URL: <https://www.stat.gov.az/>; accessed on 20 April 2022).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the numerical variables used

Indicators	Mean		Median		Standard deviation		Min-Max					
	2000	2006	2015-2017	2000	2006	2015-2017	2000	2006	2015-2017			
Age	30.5	31.1	34.87	31	31	35	9.855	10.27	6.622	15-49	15-49	18-54
Education (years)	9.9	10.61	-	10	10	-	3.926	2.636	-	0-16	0-20	-
Wealth index	2.965	2.882	-	3	3	-	1.422	1.367	-	1-5	1-5	-
Number of children	1.837	1.606	2.448	2	2	2	1.862	1.578	0.928	0-15	0-10	0-7
Age at birth of first child	22.75	22.37	23.46	22	22	23	3.762	3.862	4.549	13-42	12-42	13-42

Source: constructed by the authors based on the data from MICS 2000, DHS 2006, and MLSP 2015-2017 surveys

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the binary variables used

Variables	Year of survey	City (Proportion of urban population)		Highedu (Proportion of people with university degree)		Work (Proportion of employed population)		Over 2 child (Proportion of population with more than 2 children)		Daughters (Proportion of population with first two daughters)					
		2000	2006	2015-2017	2000	2006	2015-2017	2000	2006	2015-2017	2000	2006	2015-2017		
1	56%	53%	43%	29%	11%	23%	-	-	39%	35%	28%	45%	21%	12%	26%
0	44%	47%	57%	71%	89%	77%	-	-	61%	65%	72%	55%	79%	88%	74%

Source: constructed by the authors based on the data from MICS 2000, DHS 2006, and MLSP surveys.

Figure 4. Distribution of respondents by the number of children in the household for 2000, 2006, and 2015-2017. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on the data from MICS 2000, DHS 2006, and MLSP surveys.

Differences in the sample structure of the three surveys limit the ability to compare the results. Nevertheless, for lack of more recent MICS and DHS data, we have to use the 2015-2017 survey data.

Assessing the relationship between socio-economic factors and fertility characteristics

This section is divided into three parts, each presenting the results of model calculation based on the data from one of the surveys. For each sample, a correlation matrix was analysed, and several models were constructed to identify the relationship between the large-family indicators and socio-economic and demographic variables. The Annex gives the description of all the variables.

A study based on MICS 2000 data

To understand the relationships between the variables and the subsequent construction of models, it is required to first analyse the correlation matrix (Fig. 5). It presents the main variables, and since one of the hypotheses relates to factors affecting the number of children born, let us look at which regressors correlate with the variable *child* (number of children). A potential positive relationship can be seen between the number of children in the family and the respondent’s age, which is plausible because it takes time to have more children. At the same time, there is a negative relationship with the household wealth, mother’s level of education and urban residence. Also, there is a significant relationship between being in a higher wealth quantile and urban residence. This relationship may affect the estimation of the final model coefficients, and to rule out bias in the estimates, a test for multicollinearity was performed for each model; all the tests showed that there was none.

Figure 5. Correlation matrix of the numerical variables used. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on the MICS 2000 survey data.

The variable *groups*⁴ was taken as a dependent variable and the sample was limited by the number of children. Only respondents with two, three or four children were left in the sample. These respondents, according to the variable *groups*, were divided into three groups: 1, 2, 3, respectively. This was done so that the groups could be analysed separately. When interpreting the binary variables, we assume that, for example, if there is a negative coefficient preceding the variable referring to higher education, the probability of having more children decreases compared to people without higher education.

Table 3 summarises the results of different model specifications for estimating the probability of transitioning to higher birth orders.

The logic of the model development was as follows: first, variables related to economic factors such as urban residence, respondent’s education, household wealth, and attributes of wealth, such as possession of a radio, TV set, car, and electricity, were included in the model. Then social factors were included, such as daughter preference and use of modern contraception. Finally, the last model included the variable *agegroup* related to the respondent falling into one of the seven five-year age groups. A probit model with a similar set of variables was also developed for comparison with the logit model.

The following model appeared to be the best one in terms of correct predictions (58.4%), which is above the minimum threshold of 50%:

$$groups = city + highedu + wealth + car + electricity + radio + tv + refrigerator + daughters + famplan + agegroup + \epsilon$$

⁴ There are three groups by the number of children. First group: 2 children, second group: 3 children, third group: 4 children.

Table 3. Summary table of constructed ordered logit and probit models based on the 2000 MICS survey data

Regressors	Dependent variable: groups			
	Model 1 (oLogit)	Model 2 (oLogit)	Model 3 (oLogit)	Model 4 (oProbit)
	N = 3715	N = 3375	N = 3375	N = 3375
<i>city</i>	-0.3827*** (0.0837)	-0.3834*** (0.092)	-0.5223*** (0.0978)	-0.2968*** (0.0576)
<i>highedu</i>	-0.5775*** (0.0692)	-0.5633*** (0.0768)	-0.8354*** (0.0821)	-0.4998*** (0.0481)
<i>wealth</i>	-0.1650*** (0.0296)	-0.1716*** (0.0394)	-0.1939*** (0.0411)	-0.1195*** (0.0241)
<i>car</i>	0.1800** (0.0729)	0.1923** (0.0798)	0.2392*** (0.0839)	0.1386*** (0.0491)
<i>electricity</i>	-0.04581 (0.3481)	0.0091 (0.3128)	0.4129 (0.3236)	0.2147 (0.2042)
<i>radio</i>	0.0226 (0.0683)	0.0253 (0.0752)	-0.0685 (0.0786)	-0.0401 (0.0463)
<i>tv</i>	0.0234 (0.1058)	-0.1113 (0.11866)	-0.1514 (0.1266)	-0.0762 (0.0724)
<i>refrigerator</i>	-0.0906 (0.0885)	-0.0080 (0.0970)	-0.1714* (0.0988)	-0.1099* (0.0581)
<i>daughters</i>		1.7607*** (0.0721)	1.6337*** (0.0748)	0.9715*** (0.0433)
<i>famplan</i>		-0.2987*** (0.0719)	-0.001 (0.0774)	0.0121 (0.0451)
<i>agegroup</i>			0.6853*** (0.029)	0.4048*** (0.0166)
<i>cut1</i>	-1.4571*** (0.0391)	-1.1946*** (0.3250)	2.1229*** (0.3743)	1.2135*** (0.2308)
<i>cut2</i>	-0.0391 (0.3506)	0.3246 (0.3246)	4.0891*** (0.3803)	2.3668*** (0.2335)
<i>LnL</i>	-3925	-3232	-2916	-2912
Percentage of correct predictions	43.7% (1624)	51.0% (1720)	58.4% (1970)	58.3% (1966)

Source: constructed by the authors using his own calculations based on MICS 2000 data, employing the Gretl software package. Note: In the table, * stands for significance of the variable at 10% significance level; **, at 5% significance level; ***, at 1% significance level.

The significance of the variables can be interpreted as follows:

1. The variables *city*, *highedu*, *wealth* and *car* are significant in all the models; the negative sign in their coefficients indicates that rural residents without higher education, who are poorer than other households and do not own a car are more likely to transition to higher-order births. It is important to note the fact that the variables *radio*, *electricity*, *tv* and *refrigerator* are not significant, which may suggest that both the wealthy and lower-middle income households could afford these items in 2000.
2. The variable *daughters* is significant in all the models, indicating a high positive effect of son preference on the number of children in the household.
3. The variable *famplan* is negatively significant in Model 2 with no control for age, and insignificant in Models 3 and 4, which do control for age. This can be explained by the conservatism of older generations that prevail in the sample, which gives a general picture with an insignificant impact of this factor on the number of children in the family.

A study based on 2006 DHS data

For the primary analysis of relationships between the variables in the second database, we also constructed a correlation matrix. The 2006 database does not differ from the 2000 database in terms of the set of variables; the differences are present only in content and are caused by the different coding of higher education data.

Figure 6 shows a positive relationship between the number of children in the family and the respondent’s age. The variables related to urban residence, having a higher education degree and being part of a wealthier household group also negatively correlate with the number of children. The variable *daughters* shows a positive correlation with the variable *child*.

Figure 6. Correlation matrix of the numerical variables used. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on the AzDHS 2006 survey data.

First, a model of the dependence of respondents’ having many children on socio-economic factors was constructed with and without controlling for age. Since too little time passed between the two surveys to expect dramatic changes in the causes affecting fertility, the results of the model do not differ from the previous survey (Table 4).

Table 4. Ordered logit model based on 2006 AzDHS survey data

Regressors	Dependent variable: <i>groups</i>
	Model (oLogit)
	<i>N</i> = 4321
<i>city</i>	-0.4780*** (0.0752)
<i>highedu</i>	-0.6464*** (0.1134)
<i>wealth</i>	-0.2619*** (0.0301)
<i>car</i>	0.1992*** (0.0675)
<i>daughters</i>	1.0875*** (0.0704)
<i>famplan</i>	0.0462 (0.0629)
<i>agegroup</i>	0.5671*** (0.0222)
<i>cut1</i>	1.8493*** (0.1226)
<i>cut2</i>	3.6604*** (0.1311)
<i>LnL</i>	-3994
Percentage of correct predictions	53.6% (2318)

Source: constructed by the authors based on the AzDHS 2006 survey data using the Gretl software package. Note: In the table, * stands for significance of the variable at 10% significance level; **, at 5% significance level; ***, at 1% significance level.

Based on the results of the model selection, the following age-control model was the best:

$$groups = city + highedu + wealth + car + daughters + famplan + agegroup + \epsilon$$

The results show that urban residents are less likely to have more children than rural residents, which may suggest increasing economic and social differentiation between urban and rural areas. Conversely, the coefficient preceding the son preference variable is lower for this year compared to the previous year, suggesting a decreasing impact of son preference on fertility.

A study based on the data from the 2015-2017 MLSP survey

The correlation matrix of the 2015-2017 data presents the main variables (Fig. 7). A potential positive relationship between the number of children in the family and the respondent’s age can be seen, which is plausible and was already observed in the past data. A positive relationship was also observed for the variable *daughters* which may imply a potential dependence of the number of births on the son preference in the family.

Figure 7. Correlation matrix of the numerical variables used. *Source:* constructed by the authors based on the data from 2015-2017 MLSP survey.

The age structure of the sample is similar to that of the entire Azerbaijani population, as seen in Figure 8, but the data for the youngest and oldest ages are not representative. Therefore, it can be concluded that the sample is selective. This conclusion does not affect the overall survey, but when analysing the rejuvenation of fertility, it should be taken into account that young cohorts have not yet fully pursued their reproductive intentions and, because of this, the graphical spread of first births is limited, as only respondents over 34 years old were included. For them, the “first birth” event has either already happened or is unlikely to happen.

Table 5 presents the results of model fitting for the 2015-2017 data. Compared to the samples from previous years, the MLSP survey includes additional variables Reasons and Purpose, which respectively denote the reason the family did not have more children than they currently do, and the purpose respondents had in having a child.

Figure 8. Age structure of women in reproductive age in Azerbaijan in 2019 and according to the sample data (%). *Source:* constructed by the authors using the data from the 2015–2017 MLSP survey and data from the State Statistical Committee (URL: <https://www.stat.gov.az/>; accessed on 20 April 2022).

Only the variables relating to the socio-economic component of the study, namely education, work, place of residence (urban or rural) and whether the first two children are daughters, were included in the baseline model. These variables, even when controlling for age, remain significant at the 1% significance level while the directionality of the regressors is the same in all the models. The second model included reasons (*Reason*) why respondents do not have more children than they do; reasons 5 and 6⁵ were specifically selected, other reasons being discarded due to insignificance across the models. The same selection was made for the variables *Purpose* related to respondents’ goals in having a child. When controlling for age, all socio-economic variables are still significant, indicating the weight of these factors in the sample.

As a result, the following model appears to be the best one in terms of [correct] predictions and the log likelihood function, therefore both the subsequent interpretation and tests will be performed on this model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{groups} = & \text{city} + \text{highedu} + \text{work} + \text{daughters} + \text{Reason5} + \text{Reason6} + \text{Purpose1} + \\
 & + \text{Purpose2} + \text{Purpose3} + \text{Purpose6} + \text{age}
 \end{aligned}$$

The baseline socio-economic variables can be interpreted as follows:

1. The variables *city*, *highedu*, *work* have a negative coefficient: the respondent urban resident is more likely to have fewer children compared to the rural resident. The same is the case with higher education and having a permanent job. The greatest coefficient value is seen preceding the variable *work*. This means that working women in the sample are most likely to have fewer children than unemployed women.

5 Continuing education and financial hardship, respectively.

Table 5. Summary table of constructed ordered logit models based on the data from the MLSP 2015-2017 survey

Regressors	Dependent variable: <i>groups</i>			
	Model 1 (oLogit) <i>N</i> = 1373	Model 2 (oLogit) <i>N</i> = 1373	Model 3 (oLogit) <i>N</i> = 1373	Model 4 (oLogit) <i>N</i> = 1373
<i>city</i>	-0.4488*** (0.1148)	-0.4842*** (0.1159)	-0.4951*** (0.1181)	-0.5299*** (0.1195)
<i>highedu</i>	-0.7389*** (0.1336)	-0.6625*** (0.1371)	-0.6665*** (0.1408)	-0.7203*** (0.1412)
<i>work</i>	-0.7680*** (0.1181)	-0.8112*** (0.1248)	-0.6730*** (0.1298)	-0.8104*** (0.1341)
<i>daughters</i>	0.9942*** (0.1182)	0.9626*** (0.1196)	0.9749*** (0.1200)	0.9983*** (0.1200)
<i>Reason5</i>		-0.6231*** (0.1464)	-0.7413*** (0.1682)	-0.7126*** (0.1684)
<i>Reason6</i>		-0.8568*** (0.1324)	-0.9941*** (0.1602)	-0.8884*** (0.1609)
<i>Purpose1</i>			0.3427*** (0.1313)	0.3633*** (0.1317)
<i>Purpose2</i>			0.2571** (0.1258)	0.2284* (0.1261)
<i>Purpose3</i>			0.4245*** (0.1309)	0.3577*** (0.1309)
<i>Purpose6</i>			0.5983*** (0.1817)	0.6425*** (0.1826)
<i>age</i>				0.05944*** (0.009264)
<i>cut1</i>	-0.3526*** (0.08949)	-0.9156*** (0.1276)	-0.4310*** (0.1477)	1.622*** (0.3507)
<i>cut2</i>	2.265*** (0.1262)	1.776*** (0.1492)	2.332*** (0.1732)	4.449*** (0.3771)
<i>LnL</i>	-1167	-1144	-1121	-1101
Percentage of correct predictions	58.8% (808)	59.0% (810)	61.0% (838)	61.2% (840)

Source: constructed by the authors based on data from the MLSP 2015-2017 survey. Note: In the table, * stands for significance of the variable at 10% significance level; **, at 5% significance level; ***, at 1% significance level.

2. The variable *daughters* denoting that the first two children are daughters, conversely, has a positive coefficient, which can be interpreted as a higher probability of having more children overall if the first two children were daughters.
3. The variables *Reason5* and *Reason6* have a unidirectional negative effect on the probability of being in a higher group relative to births. Recall that *Reason5* refers to the respondent not willing to have more children because of continuing their education. *Reason6* refers to the family's financial hardship. Thus, financial hardship and the inclination to continue education negatively affect the probability of having more children.
4. All the variables *Purpose* (1; 2; 3; 6) have a positive coefficient in Model 4, with the sixth having the maximum weight. Aggregating all the variables, we find that, all other things being equal, those who choose to have a child for reasons of strengthening family ties, or not to be left alone in their old age, or to carry on the family, or especially to get a helper, are more likely to have more children than in other cases.

Limitations of the models

The present study has several limitations. First, the geographical data representativeness is compromised by the exclusion of the city of Baku from the last sample analysed. Given Baku's key role as the economic and cultural centre of Azerbaijan and its significant share of the country's population, its absence from the sample may lead to potential distortion in the interpretation of national demographic trends.

Second, the age composition of the sample leaves the cohort aged 15–19 years out of the analysis, which limits the ability to fully understand the onset of the reproductive period and its impact on overall fertility rates. This is particularly critical in the context of studying early reproductive activity and its socio-economic determinants.

The third limitation relates to the nature of the data used. The lack of panel data and differences in the composition of respondents between the three samples make it difficult to conduct a sustained analysis of changes in individual reproductive behaviour. This limits the ability of this study to identify dynamic patterns and causal relationships in reproductive behaviour.

In addition, working with data on current and past contraceptive use as explanatory variables requires caution. Data from the questions CU3 in MICS and V302 in DHS may not fully capture the complex reproductive behaviour of respondents over time, especially given changes in access to and preferences for methods of contraception.

Using the data from the new MICS and MLSP surveys will ensure better representativeness and relevance of information. Furthermore, there is a need to examine the intervals between marriage and first birth and the intervals between successive births, which can offer valuable insights into the dynamics of reproductive behaviour in the context of socio-economic and cultural changes. Investigating the potential impact of selective abortion on demographic trends is also a key aspect for understanding reproductive strategies in the region. Finally, a comparative analysis of data from other countries such as Turkey, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan will identify unique and common factors influencing reproductive behaviours in a broad regional context. Such multidimensional studies promise to improve our understanding of complex fertility dynamics and form the basis for developing more effective family planning and health policies.

Findings and conclusion

As a result of the empirical study, the first hypothesis about the negative impact of certain socio-economic factors on fertility was fully confirmed: the probability of transition to birth orders higher than two children decreases if the respondent is an urban resident, has higher education, is employed at the time of the study and if the household is in a higher wealth quartile compared to other families. Also, the dynamic change in the impact of factors showed that even with the city of Baku absent from the 2015-2017 survey, the impact of urban residence on having many children in the family increased over the years. Table 6 gives a comparative analysis of the impact of each indicator for each database.

Table 6. Summary table of the relationships between having many children in the family and particular factors, based on three years of research

Dependent variable – having two or more children in the family	2000	2006	2015–2017
Urban residence	-.***	-.***	-.***
Mother's higher education	-.***	-.***	-.***
Higher wealth	-.***	-.***	N/A
Family owns a car	+***	+**	N/A
First two children are daughters	+***	+***	+***
Use of contraception	Const	Const	N/A
Age group	+***	+***	+***

Source: constructed by the authors based on data from MICS 2000, DHS 2006, MLSP 2015-2017 surveys.

By aggregating all the additional variables for the 2015-2017 survey, we find that, all other things being equal, those who choose to have a child for reasons of strengthening family ties, or not to be left alone in their old age, or to carry on the family, or especially to get a helper are likely to have more children.

Modernisation factors, namely the increase in fertility because of higher educational attainments along the lines of the Nordic countries (Jalovaara et al. 2019), have not affected Azerbaijan so far.

The second hypothesis was fully confirmed: the son preference effect has a positive impact on having many children. Families where the first two children are daughters are more inclined to have a third and fourth child, the rationale being preference for sons as the ones to carry on the family and the family name and to be potential helpers in parents' old age. For comparison, a study conducted in Kyrgyzstan (Kazenin 2020) produced similar results, which suggests similarity between the issues at hand.

This study makes a new contribution to better understanding the evolution of child sex preference in Azerbaijan, with expanding the scope of analysis previously encountered in the works of scholars such as Avdeev (2015) and Guilimoto (2012). Unlike the above-mentioned studies, which often focus on the impact of this factor on prenatal sex selection, this study delves into the specifics of the factors of having many children. The study shows that

son preference, contrary to expectations, can stimulate fertility growth in the short term by increasing the probability of having a third and fourth child in families where the first two children are daughters.

The effect of using modern family planning methods was rejected for all constructed models when controlling for age, which may suggest that contraceptive methods are ineffective. Also problematic is the wording of the question that was posed to respondents, namely, “Have you ever used modern methods of contraception?” The respondents who answered ‘yes’ to this question were not necessarily using contraception on a regular basis. Corrective questions or rephrasing are needed to better determine the reason for non-significance.

It is likely that, in the future, women with higher education who are opposed to induced abortion would become a more common phenomenon, which will lead to late first births and a reduced fertility rate in general. To study this process, it is necessary to improve the study conducted by Azerbaijan’s Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population by making the following amendments:

1. The survey should be conducted more often (once a year) and with the same respondents so that panel data could be collected, which will allow for more accurate econometric calculations. Given the uneven urban and rural development, the panel data analysis will help to produce specialised results for each district.
2. Respondents under 20 years of age and respondents without children should be included in the sample. These groups are absent from the sample according to Figure 8, which may entail a risk of errors because the data set is not representative of the country under study.
3. A corrective question should be included in the questionnaire about whether the respondent was working before the pregnancy and, if the respondent is currently employed, what is the reason for that being so (financial hardship, pursuit of fulfilment, etc.).
4. A question on the use of modern methods of contraception should be included in the questionnaire, the best choice being “Currently using family planning methods” (CU3) from the MICS survey.
5. A question about the date of registration of the respondent’s marriage should be included in the questionnaire for further study of intervals between marriage and first birth.
6. The DHS wealth index should be included in the survey. This involves adding a series of questions about the household’s possession of certain items (a TV set, computer, etc.). That would then be used to group respondents into five quintiles⁶. This index will help to categorise respondents by their wealth without posing a direct question on their income.
7. A question should be included in the survey about whether there are grandmothers in the family who could help with child-rearing.

The above additions will not only help to improve the accuracy of results of follow-up studies, but also draw up specific action plans for each population group in each of the districts of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

6 Details of the index construction are explained in the following DHS paper (Rutstein 2015).

Bibliography

- Avdeev A (2015) Population situation analysis: Beyond the Demographic Transition in Azerbaijan, UNFPA/UNDP, Baku, 180 pp.
- Basu D, De Jong R (2010) Son targeting fertility behavior: Some consequences and determinants. *Demography* 47: 521–536. <https://doi.org/10.1353/dem.0.0110>
- Becker GS, Lewis HG (1973) On the Interaction between the Quantity and Quality of Children. *Journal of Political Economy* 81 (2): S279–S288. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1840425>
- Becker HS (1960) Notes on the Concept of Commitment. *American Journal of Sociology* 66: 32–42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/222820>
- Bongaarts J, Hodgson D (2022) Fertility transition in the developing world. Springer Nature, 144 pp.
- Day C (2018) Inverse J Effect of Economic Growth on Fertility: A Model of Gender Wages and Maternal Time Substitution. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, Springer 39 (4): 577–587. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-018-9578-3>
- Duthé G, Meslé F, Vallin J, Badurashvili I, Kuyumjyan K (2012) High Sex Ratios at Birth in the Caucasus: Modern Technology to Satisfy Old Desires. *Population and Development Review* 38 (3): 487–501. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2012.00513.x>
- Ferreira Francisco HG, Schady Norbert (2009) Aggregate Economic Shocks, Child Schooling, and Child Health. *The World Bank Research Observer* 24 (2): 147–181. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lkp006>
- Guilmoto CZ (2012) Son Preference, Sex Selection, and Kinship in Vietnam. *Population and Development Review* 38 (1): 31–54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2012.00471.x>
- Guilmoto CZ (2013) Sex Imbalances at Birth in Armenia: Demographic evidence and analysis. UNFPA. URL: <https://eeca.unfpa.org/en/publications/sex-imbances-birth-armenia>.
- Hotz VJ, Klerman JA, Willis RJ (1997) The economics of fertility in developed countries. *Handbook of Population and Family Economics* / Edited by M. Rosenzweig & O. Stark. Vol. 1, Part A. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 275–347 pp. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-003X\(97\)80024-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-003X(97)80024-4).
- Jalovaara M, Neyer G, Andersson G, Dahlberg J, Dommermuth L, Fallesen P, Lappegård, T (2019) Education, Gender, and Cohort Fertility in the Nordic Countries. *European Journal of Population* 35: 563–586. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10680-018-9492-2>
- Jayachandran S, Kuziemko I (2011) Why do mothers breastfeed girls less than boys? Evidence and implications for child health in India. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 126 (3): 1485–1538. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjr029>
- Kazenin K (2017) Vliyanie sotsial'nykh izmeneniy na rozhdadnost' v regionakh Severnogo Kavkaza [The Impact of Social Changes on Fertility in the Regions of the North Caucasus]. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2983145> (in Russian)
- Kelodjouea S (2015) Trends and determinants of unmet need for family planning in Cameroon: the role of socio-cultural context. *Sociology* 5(1): 39–52. <https://doi.org/10.17265/2159-5526/2015.01.005>
- Kozlov VA, Kazenin KI (2020) Osobennosti gendernykh otnosheniy, sotsial'noe neravenstvo i rozhdadnost' v stranakh Sredney Azii: opyt statisticheskogo issledovaniya [Features of Gender Relations, Social Inequality, and Fertility in Central Asian Countries: A Statistical Study Experience]. Russian Economic Congress. URL: https://www.iep.ru/files/text/other/REK2020_Kazenin.pdf (in Russian)
- LeVine RA, LeVine SE, Richman A, Uribe FMT, Correa CS, Miller PM (1991) Women's schooling and child care in the demographic transition: A Mexican case study. *The Population and Development Review* 17: 459–496. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1971950>

- Li Hongbin, Junjian Yi, Junsen Zhang (2011) Estimating the Effect of the One-Child Policy on the Sex Ratio Imbalance in China: Identification Based on the Difference-in-Differences. *Demography* 48: 1535–57. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41408201>.
- Maitra P (2004) Effect of Socioeconomic Characteristics on Age at Marriage and Total Fertility in Nepal. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition* 22 (1): 84–96. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23499013>
- Michael M, King L, Guo L, McKee M, Richardson E, Stuckler D (2013) The Mystery of Missing Female Children in the Caucasus: An Analysis of Sex Ratios by Birth Order. *International Perspectives on Sexual and Reproductive Health* 39 (2): 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1363/3909713>
- Pörtner CC (2022) Birth Spacing and Fertility in the Presence of Son Preference and Sex-Selective Abortions: India's Experience Over Four Decades. *Demography* 59 (1): 61–88. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00703370-9580703>
- Shukyurov AS (2020) Demograficheskiy perekhod v Azerbaidzhane [Demographic Transition in Azerbaijan]. Master's thesis, Moscow: National Research University Higher School of Economics. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12459.46889> (in Russian)
- Trussell J, Martin LG, Feldman R, Palmore JA, Concepcion M, Abu Bakar D (1985) Determinants of birth-interval length in the Philippines, Malaysia, and Indonesia: A hazard-model analysis. *Demography* 22 (2): 145–168. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2061175>
- Verdiyeva N (2019) How the population of the Republic of Azerbaijan is ageing: causes and potential for social and economic development. *Population and Economics* 3 (3): 43–73. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.3.e47233>
- Whitworth A, Stephenson R (2002) Birth spacing, sibling rivalry and child mortality in India. *Social Science & Medicine* 55: 2107–2119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536\(02\)00002-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536(02)00002-3)
- Yüksel-Kaptanoğlu I, Eryurt MA, Koç I, Çavlin A (2014) Mechanisms behind the Skewed Sex Ratio at Birth in Azerbaijan: Qualitative and Quantitative Analyses. UNFPA, p. 78. URL: <https://azerbaijan.un.org/en/51843-mechanisms-behind-skewed-sex-ratio-birth-azerbaijan>

Other sources of information

- AzDHS, Demographic and Health Survey in Azerbaijan (2006). URL: <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/fr195/fr195.pdf> [Accessed on 10.04.2022].
- Anonymized Data from the Survey of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2015, 2016, 2017 URL: <https://sosial.gov.az/> [Accessed on 10.03.2022].
- Website of the State Statistics Committee of Azerbaijan. URL: <https://www.stat.gov.az/> [Accessed on 10.03.2022].
- Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys in Azerbaijan by UNICEF (2000). URL: <https://mics.unicef.org/surveys> [Accessed on 10.04.2022]
- Rutstein SO (2015) Steps to constructing the new DHS Wealth Index // Rockville, MD: ICF International. T. 6. URL: https://dhsprogram.com/programming/wealth%20index/Steps_to_constructing_the_new_DHS_Wealth_Index.pdf
- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2019). World Population Prospects 2019, Volume I: Comprehensive Tables (ST/ESA/SER.A/426). URL: https://population.un.org/wpp/publications/Files/WPP2019_Volume-I_Comprehensive-Tables.pdf [Accessed on 10.04.2022]

Annex

Table A1. Explanation of variables used in the study

Study variables for the 2000 data	
<i>City</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 or 0 if the respondent is an urban resident or a rural resident, respectively.
<i>Age</i>	A numerical variable that refers to the respondent's age at the time of the survey.
<i>Age.Group</i>	A categorical variable from 1 to 7, related to the 5-year age group that the respondent belongs to at the time of the survey: [15-19] – 1, etc.
<i>Wealth</i>	A categorical variable that refers to categorisation into 5 groups according to household wealth: 1 – the poorest, 5 – the wealthiest.
<i>Car</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the household owns a car and 0 otherwise.
<i>Year</i>	A numerical variable that refers to the respondent's year of birth.
<i>High.edu.</i>	A binary variable taking the value 1 if the respondent has incomplete higher education, higher education or college diploma; and 0 in all other cases (primary education, 9 grades of high school, vocational training, technical school).
<i>Child</i>	A numerical variable that refers to the number of children.
<i>Over2child</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the respondent has more than 2 children and 0 otherwise.
<i>Groups</i>	A categorical variable that refers to categorisation of respondents into groups: 1 – the family has 2 children; 2 – the family has 3 children; 3 – the family has 4 or more children.
<i>Daughters</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the first two children in the family are daughters, or 0 otherwise.
<i>Birth.age1</i>	A numerical variable that refers to the mother's age at last birthday at the birth of her first child.
<i>fam.plan</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the female respondent uses family planning methods, or 0 otherwise.
Additional and corrected variables for the 2006 data	
<i>High.edu.</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the respondent has completed secondary education, higher education or college, or 0 otherwise (primary education, 9 grades of high school, vocational training, technical school).

Additional and corrected variables for the 2015-2017 data*

<i>High.edu.</i>	A binary variable taking the value 1 if the respondent has incomplete higher education, bachelor's, master's degree or doctoral degree, or 0 otherwise (primary education, 9 grades of high school, vocational training, technical school, college).
<i>Work</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the respondent is employed in the civil service or private sector or is self-employed, or 0 otherwise.
<i>Knowgend</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the respondent wishes to know the child's sex prior to birth, or 0 otherwise.
<i>Unexpect.preg</i>	A binary variable that takes the value 1 if the respondent decides to continue unintended pregnancy, or 0 otherwise.
<i>Reason(n)</i>	<p>Binary variables referring to the answers to the question "Why don't you have more children in your family than you do?":</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The partner objects. 2. Pressure from relatives. 3. Unemployment. 4. Career prospects. 5. Continuing education. 6. Financial hardship. 7. Giving the child a lot of attention. 8. Health. 9. Age. 10. Living conditions.
<i>Purpose(n)</i>	<p>Binary variables referring to the answers to the question "Which of the following reasons for having a baby do you most agree with?":</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthening family ties. 2. Not to be left alone in old age. 3. To carry on the lineage. 4. Gain respect from others. 5. To fulfil the expectations of relatives. 6. To have a helper at your disposal. 7. So that the child develops together with the society. 8. To give the baby to childless families. 9. Medical reasons. 10. Desire to realise herself as a woman.

Source: constructed by the authors based on the MICS 2000, AzDHS 2006 and MLSP 2015-2017 survey questionnaires. *Note:* The variables fam.plan, Wealth, Car, electricity, refrigerator are absent from the 2015–2017 data due to a different survey method.

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